

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Brown planthopper			Green leaf-hopper	White-backed plant-hopper	Zigzag leaf-hopper	Yellow stem borer	Striped stem borer	Leaf-folder	Case-worm	Whorl maggot
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3								
IR34	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR36	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR38	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR40	R	MR	S	MR	S	S	MR	R	S	S	MR
IR42	R	R	S	MR ^d	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR43	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR44	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	R	S	S	S
IR45	R	S	R	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR46	R	S ^b	R	MR ^d	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR48	R	R	S	MR	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	R	MR ^c	R	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR52	R	R	MR ^c	R	MR	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR54	R	R	S	R	S	S	MR	MR	S	S	S

^aReplicated experiments. Hopper resistance based on greenhouse evaluation of seedlings; yellow and striped stem borer resistance based on screenhouse evaluation of 40- to 70-day-old plants; leaffolder and caseworm resistance based on the reaction of 30- and 11-day-old plants in the greenhouse; whorl maggot resistance based on field observations at 30 days after transplanting. Ratings, based on Standard Evaluation System for Rice: 1-3 = resistant (R), 5-7 = moderately resistant (MR), and 9 = susceptible (S). ^bIR46 has field resistance to biotype 2. ^cReactions to biotype 3 vary, occasionally susceptible and often resistant. ^dOccasional susceptible reactions.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Vegetative regeneration in floating rice

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Two types of cuttings and two planting methods were used to study vegetative regeneration for retrieval of floating rice plants. Healthy stems were cut into sets, with two open nodes in top cuttings and two to three nodes in mid-stem cuttings. Cuttings were planted both vertically

and horizontally.

Top cuttings (48) with just-sprouting and developed aquatic roots were planted in submerged soil (20 cm water) 10 cm apart in vertical planting, and end-to-end in horizontal planting with 20 cm interrow spacing. Unsprouted mid-stem cuttings (48) were inserted straight in vertical planting and planted in furrows in horizontal planting.

In top cuttings, dormant buds sprouted on day 5 and tillers were seen after 1 week. In horizontal planting, the

middle bud sprouted at a 75-98° angle.

In vertical planting, shoots emerged from the lower and middle buds parallel to the cutting.

Sets were transplanted 1 week after emergence and waterlogging was maintained. Performance of the regenerated plants was compared with that of normal plants (see table).

Survival was highest with vertical planting. Yield characteristics were very low, but might be improved by adjusting planting time. ■

Performance of floating rice stem cuttings and normal plants at Ghaghraghat, India.

Treatment	Survival (%)	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	100-grain weight (g)	Yield per Plant (g)
Stem - top cuttings, developed roots, planted vertically	82.5	94.0	8.6	22.6	118	18.1	12.7	2.2	4.0
Stem - top cuttings, developed roots, planted horizontally	79.1	91.1	6.8	21.5	107	20.4	19.1	2.2	3.4
Stem - top cuttings, sprouted roots, planted vertically	79.1	93.8	6.4	21.3	99	19.8	16.5	2.2	3.3
Stem - top cuttings, sprouted roots, planted horizontally	82.5	86.7	4.0	22.5	105	20.5	16.6	2.2	3.5
Mid-stems planted vertically	73.7	83.3	6.3	19.3	105	25.4	17.6	2.1	2.7
Mid-stems planted horizontally	58.8	90.6	5.6	22.2	104	25.6	15.3	2.1	2.0
Normal plant	-	425.0	10.4	27.4	154	15.3	24.1	2.5	28.6